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Rational for the possible introduction of Haemophilus influenzae vaccine into the Iraq vaccination program

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Abstract

Bacterial meningitis remains one of the most potentially serious infections in infants and children with high risk of acute complications and chronic morbidity. Haemophilus influenzae was the most common bacterial pathogens causing meningitis during the first year of life before the introduction of vaccines against Haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib). The wide spread use of Hib vaccines was associated with marked reduction in the frequency of Haemophilus infection, and Haemophilus influenzae is no longer the most common bacterial pathogens causing meningitis during the first year of life in many geographic areas such as UK and USA. In Iraq the precise and even the rough contribution of Haemophilus influenzae and other bacterial pathogens to acute bacterial meningitis and acute CNS infection in general remains unknown. The aim of this paper is to discuss the rational for the possible introduction of Hib vaccine into the Iraq vaccination program based on the success associated with the introduction of the Hib vaccines into the developed countries vaccination program.

Keywords: Bacterial meningitis- Iraq vaccination program- Haemophilus influenzae type b vaccine.

Haemophilus influenzae was first recognized in 1892 by Pfeiffer, who erroneously concluded that the bacterium was the cause of influenza. The bacterium is a small (1- by 0.3-um) gram-negative organism of variable shape; hence, it is often described as a pleomorphic coccobacillus. Six major serotypes of H. influenzae have been identified (a-f) they are identified by antigenically distinct polysaccharide capsules. Strains lack a polysaccharide capsule and are referred to as nontypable strains. Type b and nontypable strains are the most relevant strains clinically, although encapsulated strains other than type b can cause disease. The antigenically distinct type b capsule is a linear polymer composed of ribosyl-ribitol phosphate. Strains of H. influenzae type b (Hib) cause disease primarily in infants and children under the age of 6 years. Nontypable strains are primarily mucosal pathogens, although the incidence of invasive disease caused by these strains is increasing. The most serious manifestation of infection with H. influenzae is **meningitis**. Haemophilus influenzae causes also epiglottitis (a life-threatening infection involving cellulitis of the epiglottis and supraglottic tissues), Cellulitis, and

pneumonia in infants. Several less common invasive conditions can be important clinical manifestations of Hib infection in children. These include osteomyelitis, septic arthritis, pericarditis, orbital cellulitis, endophthalmitis, urinary tract infection, abscesses, and bacteremia without an identifiable focus. Infections due to *Haemophilus influenzae* are unusual among patients older than 6 years. The most reliable method for establishing a diagnosis of *Haemophilus influenzae* infection is recovery of the organism in culture. The CSF of a patient in whom meningitis is suspected should be subjected to Gram's staining and culture. The presence of gram-negative coccobacilli in Gram-stained CSF is strong evidence for Hib meningitis. Recovery of the organism from CSF confirms the diagnosis. Cultures of other normally sterile body fluids, such as blood, joint fluid, pleural fluid, pericardial fluid, and subdural effusion, are confirmatory in other infections. Detection of PRP is an important adjunct to culture in rapid diagnosis. Immunoelectrophoresis, latex agglutination, coagglutination, and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay are effective in detecting PRP. These assays are particularly helpful when patients have received prior antimicrobial therapy and thus are especially likely to have negative cultures [1].

Childhood bacterial meningitis:

Bacteria are still responsible for many cases of meningitis throughout the world, and bacterial meningitis remains one of the most potentially serious infections in infants and children with high risk of acute complications and chronic morbidity. The mortality from these infections has declined in recent years, but there is

disturbing evidence that the long term consequences of meningitis early in life may be worse than previously thought. Attenuated immunologic response to specific pathogens associated with young age is probably the most important risk factor for meningitis. Approximately 95% of all cases of meningitis occur between 1 month and 12 month of age. In many geographic areas the three most common bacterial pathogens causing meningitis are *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Streptococcus meningitis*, and *Neisseria meningitidis*. *Haemophilus influenzae* was the most common bacterial pathogens causing meningitis during the first year of life before the introduction of vaccines against *Haemophilus influenzae* type b (Hib). The wide spread use of Hib vaccines was associated with marked reduction in the frequency of *Haemophilus* infection, and *Haemophilus influenzae* is no longer the most common bacterial pathogens causing meningitis during the first year of life in many geographic areas such as UK and USA [2, 3, 4, 5,6].

The pattern of childhood bacterial meningitis in Iraqi children

In Iraq the precise and even the rough contribution of *Haemophilus influenzae* and other bacterial pathogens to acute bacterial meningitis and acute CNS infection in general remains unknown. It was not possible to find any published literature reporting the pattern of childhood bacterial meningitis. Many factors have been precluding the estimation of the contribution of *Haemophilus influenzae* and other bacterial pathogens to acute bacterial meningitis in Iraqi children. According to our experience at the University Hospital in Al Kadhimiya (One of the three large teaching hospitals in

Baghdad), the factors that have been precluding the determination of the pattern of childhood bacterial meningitis in Iraqi children include:

1-The vast majority of our patients were receiving antibiotics for several days before referral and the CSF microscopic examination and CSF cultures didn't reveal the causative organism. Remembering that it has been shown that virtually all patients will have sterilization of the CSF within 24 hours of the initiation of antibiotics [5]. In most instances the clinical suspicion of bacterial meningitis was supported by finding of CSF pleocytosis with or without low CSF sugar or elevated proteins together with a satisfactory and relatively early response to antibiotics that cover the three common pathogens that are responsible for bacterial meningitis in many geographic areas of the world.

During the 1990s ampicillin and chloramphenicol were the most commonly used antibiotics in Iraqi hospitals for the treatment of cases of suspected bacterial meningitis. During the previous 8 years, there has been an increased use of third generation cephalosporins especially cefotaxime in patients with diagnosis of bacterial meningitis.

2-Iraq had been in a continuous turmoil during more than two decades there had been a continuous series of financial, social, and political crises. Successive wars and long blockade played an important role in the generation of these complex and continuous crises. These crises were associated with poor recording systems in hospitals, deterioration in residents training programme together with a marked deterioration in the academic and research performances in Iraqi

hospitals compared with many other countries with much lower resources such as India and Pakistan.

The introduction of the Haemophilus influenzae vaccines into the developed countries vaccination program

The introduction of the Haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib) polysaccharide-conjugate vaccine into the developed countries (UK, and USA) vaccination program has had a dramatic effect. The incidence of Hib meningitis has dropped from around 2500 cases per year to less than 40 per year in some areas. Conjugate vaccines against H. influenzae type b (Hib) and N. meningitidis group C are now routinely given in the UK as part of the primary course of immunization at 2, 3 and 4 months. An effective vaccine against N. meningitidis group B is not yet available. Trials of conjugate pneumococcal vaccines are underway and may be introduced in the UK in the near future [4]. Haemophilus influenzae was once the most common cause of bacterial meningitis in the United States. The incidence of H. influenzae meningitis declined precipitously following the introduction of the H. influenzae type b (Hib) vaccine in 1987, and H. influenzae now accounts for <10% of bacterial meningitis cases [7].

Hib vaccines have been shown to be safe and immunogenic during the first month of life. The efficacy rate of Hib vaccines ranged from 70-100%. According to the committee on infectious diseases of the American academy of Pediatrics recommendation, all children should be immunized with Haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib) vaccine at

about 2 month of age or as soon as possible later[8,9,10].

Rational for the possible introduction of Haemophilus influenzae vaccine into the Iraq vaccination program

Many of the new therapies and preventive measures including new antibiotics(e.g. third generation cephalosporins) and new vaccines(e.g. Hepatitis B vaccine) have been introduced in Iraq with a beneficial effect based on outside researches and experiences rather than Iraqi researches and clinical studies. Obviously, improvement in the specific diagnosis of bacterial meningitis can't be witnessed in Iraqi hospital in the near future. It seems logic that Hib vaccines should be introduced into the Iraq vaccination program depending on evidences available from outside Iraq.

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